

Table S1. Correlation between physicochemical properties of cultivation substrate and agronomic performance of *Pleurotus ostreatus* mushroom.

Variable		Agronomic performance of <i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i> mushroom									
		Pearson correlation coefficient (r-value) and Significance (p-value)	Days taken for mycelia to fully colonize substrate	Days taken for primordia initiation from fully colonized substrate	Days taken to complete first flush growth	Stipe length	Pileus diameter	Fresh weight of fruiting bodies	Number of total fruiting bodies	Number of effective fruiting bodies	Biological efficiency
Physicochemical properties of cultivation substrate	Wet bulk density	r-value	0.346	0.307	0.385	0.521	.844**	-0.109	-0.19	-.109**	0.137
		p-value	0.362	0.422	0.306	0.15	0.004	0.779	0.624	0.000	0.725
	Particle density	r-value	0.205	0.38	0.502	0.295	.710*	-0.32	-0.396	-.320**	0.171
		p-value	0.596	0.313	0.168	0.44	0.032	0.401	0.292	0.000	0.66
	Porosity	r-value	-0.086	-0.211	-0.135	-0.534	-0.228	-0.178	-0.192	-.178**	0.089
		p-value	0.827	0.586	0.73	0.139	0.555	0.646	0.62	0.000	0.82
	pH	r-value	-0.505	0.096	-0.167	0.124	-.749*	0.264	0.478	.264**	-0.039
		p-value	0.165	0.805	0.667	0.75	0.02	0.493	0.193	0.000	0.92
	Moisture content	r-value	0.19	0.293	0.227	0.624	0.397	-0.263	-0.234	-.263**	0.201
		p-value	0.624	0.444	0.557	0.072	0.29	0.494	0.545	0.000	0.604
	Ash content	r-value	0.095	0.033	0.062	0.247	-0.051	0.653	0.557	.653**	0.011
		p-value	0.808	0.933	0.873	0.521	0.897	0.056	0.12	0.000	0.977
	Volatile solids content	r-value	-0.095	-0.033	-0.062	-0.247	0.051	-0.653	-0.557	-.653**	-0.011
		p-value	0.808	0.933	0.873	0.521	0.897	0.056	0.12	0.000	0.977
	Nitrogen	r-value	-0.101	0.218	0.201	0.246	-0.3	0.637	0.593	.637**	-0.142
		p-value	0.796	0.572	0.605	0.523	0.432	0.065	0.092	0.000	0.715
	Phosphorus	r-value	0.011	0.072	0.049	0.416	-0.129	0.497	0.455	.497**	0.112
		p-value	0.978	0.853	0.9	0.265	0.741	0.173	0.219	0.000	0.775
	Potassium	r-value	0.112	-0.59	-0.58	-0.208	-0.492	.675*	0.651	.675**	0.22
		p-value	0.775	0.094	0.102	0.591	0.179	0.046	0.058	0.000	0.569
	Calcium	r-value	-0.194	0.214	0.137	0.338	-0.32	0.368	0.322	.368**	-0.092
		p-value	0.617	0.58	0.724	0.374	0.401	0.331	0.397	0.000	0.815
	Magnesium	r-value	-0.203	0.079	-0.012	0.308	-0.345	0.464	0.454	.464**	0.023
		p-value	0.6	0.84	0.975	0.42	0.363	0.208	0.22	0.000	0.953
	Iron	r-value	.731*	-0.47	-0.157	-0.211	0.059	0.511	0.3	.511**	-0.14
		p-value	0.025	0.201	0.686	0.586	0.881	0.16	0.432	0.000	0.719
	Zinc	r-value	0.333	-0.53	-0.453	-0.097	0.138	0.639	0.638	.639**	0.555
		p-value	0.381	0.142	0.221	0.805	0.724	0.064	0.065	0.000	0.121
Carbon	r-value	0.104	-0.262	-0.265	-0.212	0.359	-0.323	-0.257	-.323**	0.569	
	p-value	0.791	0.497	0.49	0.584	0.343	0.396	0.504	0.000	0.11	
Lignin	r-value	0.28	0.307	0.52	-0.093	0.498	-0.335	-0.474	-.335**	-0.24	
	p-value	0.466	0.421	0.151	0.813	0.172	0.378	0.197	0.000	0.534	
Hemicellulose	r-value	.761*	-0.641	-0.281	-0.548	0.018	0.315	0.087	.315**	-0.131	
	p-value	0.017	0.063	0.464	0.126	0.963	0.409	0.823	0.000	0.737	
Cellulose	r-value	-0.031	-0.309	-0.429	-0.131	0.168	-0.009	0.021	-0.009	.741*	
	p-value	0.937	0.419	0.249	0.736	0.667	0.981	0.958	0.372	0.022	

Note:

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level.